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Project Management handbook

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable explains how the STRATEGIC project ensures all project management processes are clearly defined and agreed at the start of the project. This is an internal document and highlights how the project will be managed.

2 General Introduction

This handbook gives an overview of important aspects of the project that members of the STRATEGIC consortium need to be aware of to successfully contribute to the project. It is based on the Grant Agreement (including all Annexes), the Consortium Agreement and experience of conducting collaborative projects.

The purpose of the project is reflected in the proposal abstract below:

The STRATEGIC project aims to co-create responsible research and innovation approach that aligns with social-cultural values, principles, contexts, needs and interests in SSA and implement capacity development plans that can strengthen the ethics and regulatory capacity to ensure responsible digital health technologies for clinical research and practice. The project will involve SSA and EU partners and stakeholders and co-create functional resources, such as the STRATEGIC training materials. The urgency of strengthening ethics and legal infrastructure for digital health technologies in SSA is due to the increasing integration of digital technologies into clinical research and practice and the potential negative impacts of these systems on patients, communities and society. While most countries in the Global North have recognised the importance of responsible digital health technologies, the ethics and regulatory capacities for addressing the ethical and legal risks of these technologies are still lacking in SSA. The overarching aim of the STRATEGIC project is to co-create a theoretically strong, empirically supported and widely consulted responsible research and innovation approach and capacity development plan and materials that can strengthen relevant ethics and regulatory institutions for clinical research and practice in SSA. It will identify and map the existing ethical and legal infrastructure in SSA, highlighting the gaps and needs; use these insights to co-create an RRI approach and co-develop and implementing trainings that will also be interested into existing training infrastructure and network. It will also establish sustainable e-community that exist beyond the project. Methodologies to be used include stakeholder engagement and co-creation strategies such as focus groups, consensus workshops and roundtable discussions.

3 Consortium Management

3.1 Management Structure

The basic purpose of project management is to ensure a level of coordination and cooperation amongst the project consortium members to ensure that project aims and objectives are realised. This includes timely reporting to the European Commission.

The management structure of the project is as follows: -

3.1.1 Project Management Structure

There are three key elements of management in the STRATEGIC project; (1) Scientific coordination, (2) Project management and (3) administrative coordination. The scientific coordinator (Ghana Health Service – GHS) oversees the core scientific activities in the project through WP1. The administrative coordinator (University of Bonn (UBO)) manages the project finances. Project manager (UoN) undertakes the overall project management. The partners involved have agreed on developing an effective and decentralised management structure based on delegated responsibilities. It is therefore the responsibility of the WP leaders to oversee tasks/deliverables in their own WP and coordinate meetings with partners who are also collaborating in the same work package.

3.1.2 Coordination Team

The coordination team is made up of the scientific coordinator, the administrative coordinator and the project management team. STRATEGIC's coordination team will provide full transparency and control of the entire project in terms of time, resources and cost tracking.

Office of the Scientific Coordinator

The office of the scientific coordinator consists of individuals working for the scientific coordinator (Ghana Health Service) and includes.....

The role of the scientific coordinator includes among other things:

- Develop detailed overall project methodology
- Connect with EDCTP
- Track progress of WPs 2-6 including the internal review of project deliverables.
- Ensure submission of deliverables on the EU participant portal as specified on the project time plan. Supervise the implementation of the work plan and ensure deliverables are submitted on time. If during the project there are any changes or delays to the submission of deliverables, these should be flagged immediately to the Project Office.
- Ensure scientific quality assurance
- Ensure that Scientific outreaches align with STRATEGIC's objectives
- Ensure submission of deliverables on the EU participant portal as specified on the project time plan.

Office of the Administrative coordinator

The office of the administrative coordinator consists of individuals working for the administrative coordinator on the STRATEGIC project. The role of the administrative coordinator includes to:

- Administer project resources and monitor project spending
- Collect reports from partners and forward the Periodic Progress Reports to the Project Officer. (Please see deliverable template in appendix).

Project Management Office

The Project management Office consists of the individuals who work for University of Nottingham in STRATEGIC Project. The mandate of the Project Management Office is to:

- Supervise the overall project management of the project
- Promote project visibility and dissemination of project results in relevant national and international forums. This is also a responsibility of all consortium partners to attend/present at conferences/workshops to promote the project.
- Organise, convene and chair project meetings of project meetings
- Circulate project meeting agenda and minutes
- Communicate with partner representatives to co-ordinate the dissemination of the project's results.
- Supervise compliance with the project handbook, e.g., use of templates, storage of data, communication and reporting.
- Convene and participate in review meetings, as required

3.1.3 General Assembly (GA)

Experience and extensive research on collaborative projects (cf. CONSIDER, SHERPA projects) have demonstrated that flat management structures are important to ensure successful collaboration and inclusion of all partners. The main decision-making body of STRATEGIC is the GA which includes all partners. The GA consists of one delegate (partner representative) from each organisation participating in the project. Participation by all partners is mandatory. The chair of the GA is UoN. The GA may decide to delegate tasks and decisions to appropriate sub-committees.

3.1.4 Partner Representative

Each partner representative will represent their organisation in the GA activities. Each partner representative must be authorised to make binding decisions on behalf of the organisation during the normal course of GA business. Partners must be clear for each meeting who represents them. Partner representatives should be authorised to make decisions on behalf of partners.

3.1.5 WP Leaders, WPs and Tasks Meetings

The consortium has nominated a WP leader for each WP. She or he is responsible for the technical and administrative coordination of the work within the assigned work package and for ensuring deliverables are submitted on time. Possible deviations in time and effort must be immediately reported to the Project Office. In addition to this, the WP leader should provide input to the end year review report and attend the subsequent review meeting with the EC project officer.

WP and task meetings will take place as required. All contributing partners are required to attend these meetings. The chair for these meetings will be the respective Coordinator, WP or task leader and it will be their responsibility to organise and circulate agenda and notes of the minutes of the meeting to all partners involved.

WP name	Lead partner	Named Partner Representative
WP1: Scientific Project Leadership	GHS	Naa-Korkor Allotey
WP2: Review of Ethics and Legal Infrastructure	GHS	Naa-Korkor Allotey
WP3: Co-design of governance approaches for responsible digital health technology	LETS	Marceline Djuidje Ngounoue
WP4: Prioritisation of sustainable ethical and legal Approaches in SSA	UEM	Mohsin Sidat
WP5: Development and implementation of Capacity development and training	EUREC	Lisa Häberlein
WP6: Dissemination, Communication and Advocacy	UEM	Celso Give
WP7: Project Coordination and Management	UBO	Dorothee Güth

Table 1: Named WP leaders

3.1.6 WP/Task Leaders

The WP/Task Leader is the representative of the partner responsible for the Work package or Task. The WP/Task Leaders are responsible for the performance of the corresponding WPs/Tasks and ensuring deliverables are submitted in time, any changes to timings should be immediately flagged to the Coordination Team and the General Assembly. WP/Task Leaders are required to attend relevant

meetings. WP/task leaders should also monitor the quality of outputs that are/will be produced (i.e., by discussing work and task plans, deliverable outlines and working drafts etc)

3.2 Meetings, Updates

In order to ensure that the project runs smoothly, there are several different types of meetings and procedures:

- There will be a General Assembly of all project members every six months. This meeting will review the project plan, allow for the consortium to agree on project decisions, discuss any major strategic changes and discuss the next steps of the project. The GA will also decide any issues related to re-allocation of budgets. Standing items of the GA meetings include:
 - o Current state of the consortium plan (financial state, deliverables and milestones, risks)
 - o Quality of collaboration (provide feedback of how the project is going so far)
 - o Update of dissemination, communications plan
 - o Research results and plans
 - o Promote discussion amongst partners on the project
 - o The next steps of the project – including partners giving presentations on how they plan to deliver their tasks going forward.
- The Project coordination team and partners will furthermore meet:
 - o Face-to-face as required
 - o By teleconference (Teams or other means) on a fortnightly basis. The teleconference will be a regular event taking place at the same time each fortnight. The GA may decide to reduce these meetings once the project has stabilised. (For example, monthly Teams meetings may be practical). Standing items on the SC agenda include:
 - § Update of project plan
 - § Internal milestones and deliverables
 - § To do list
 - § Progress since the previous meeting
 - § Publications
 - § Results of collaboration
 - § Budget
 - § General content
 - § General administrative and AOB

During these meetings all members will be expected to report their activity during the preceding period, if needed, the status of their budget and expenditure, and the progress of all internal and external deliverables and milestones. The minutes of these meetings will be written and circulated by the project manager. Please note that consortium partners have up to 1 week to comment on the minutes of the meeting, after that the minutes will be deemed accepted by project management.

4 Decision-Making, Consortium Agreement

The decision-making processes are agreed in detail in the Consortium Agreement which is based on the Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA) model agreement. Some of the most important aspects are briefly:

- Quorum 2/3 in all bodies
- Vote 2/3 on all decisions
- Veto where legitimate interests are affected (time, budget, ...)

5. Contact List

A complete list of all members of the consortium can be found in the shared workspace.

6. Planning, Reporting and Monitoring

At contractually pre-determined reporting periods (one period after 18 months) all participants will have to submit a financial claim (through the Administrative Coordinator) to the EC reporting on all costs that have been incurred to the project during the reference reporting period. Further funding for the project will only be made available when the aggregate claim has been approved by the EC.

6.1 Reporting

There are 2 reporting periods during the project at time points; (RP1) 18 months, (RP2) 36 months, the end of the project. During these periods, it will be the responsibility of all WP leaders to provide information and contribute to the overall review report, as well as providing interim financial information.

Financial cost claims need to be prepared at the end of each reporting period (18 and 36 months). All reports to the EU will need to be submitted through the participant portal.

A project file with all relevant documentation for project expenses, e.g. invoices, orders, travel claims, etc., must be maintained to prepare for those (hopefully infrequent) cases where the project is subsequently selected for an audit by the EU, which may take place up to 5 years after the end of the project.

For personnel expenditure Finance and HR departments store the original documents. It must be ensured that every person working for the project, especially on a part-time basis, has completed the necessary timesheets, signed by his/her supervisor. The original of the timesheets should be stored by the project administration.

7. Publications

STRATEGIC Project publications encompass papers or abstracts based on investigations that: (1) utilise the intellectual resources of the project; (2) utilize data collected through the project activities; or (3) rely, wholly or partially, on information obtained through project.

Authorship for all STRATEGIC Project papers will be weighted based on current effort and contribution, with claims for authorship being reasonable and self-critical. Partners or individuals with publication ideas will bring them to the attention of all project partners in a transparent way via the email list. Individuals with interest in contributing to the paper will then indicate and be included as authors.

8. Financial Issues

To comply with contractual obligations, it is important that the project is managed well in financial as well as scientific respect. This will require a basic understanding of Horizon Europea accounting and financial rules. It will also require a continuous update of all relevant data. The partners are responsible for their own budget and that they need to comply with EU accounting rules.

8.1 Basics of Horizon Europe Finance

There are a number of issues and rules that all participants in Horizon Europe projects should be aware of:

8.1 Payment Procedures:

Article 22 of the Grant Agreement and Data Sheet 4.2 set out the payments to be made by the Commission to the coordinator and by the coordinator to the consortium partners:

- One initial pre-financing (STRATEGIC pre-financing payment letter dated 27/03/2024)
- One interim-payment after the end of the first reporting period (after project month 18, 30/09/2025, within 90 days or submission of the first periodic report)
- One final payment after the end of the project (after project month 36, 31/03/2027, within 90 days of submission of the second periodic report)

8.2 Pre-Financing and Mutual Insurance Mechanism (MIM)

The aim of the pre-financing is to provide the beneficiaries with a float. It remains the property of the EU until the final payment. The amount of the STRATEGIC pre-financing payment was EUR 615,598.80. The contribution to the mutual insurance mechanism (MIM) retained by the Commission from the initial pre-financing was 5 % of the total contribution (EUR 38,474.81). This corresponds to the rate and modalities defined in point 4.2 of the data sheet.

8.3 Reimbursement of Eligible Costs

The interim payment and the final payment reimburse the eligible costs incurred in implementing the measure in the corresponding reporting periods. These are personnel costs based on time sheets and purchase costs based on supporting documents (travel and subsistence, other goods, works and services). The flat rate for indirect costs is 25% of the eligible direct costs.

8.4 Project Accounting

According to article 21 of the Grant Agreement the interim payment and the final payment are based on the financial statements of each beneficiary. The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category. Prior to the final payment, the amount paid will never exceed 90 % of a partners' maximum grant amount.

By signing the financial statements directly via the EU funding and tenders portal, the partners confirm that the information provided is complete, reliable and true and that the costs claimed are eligible.

8.5 Financial Forecasting

In order to ensure that the project is under control in financial (and scientific) respect, the office of the administrative coordinator will closely monitor progress. With regards to project finance this will require the administrative coordinator to have a clear idea of the expected state of the budget, which can then be compared with the actual state. For this purpose, the administrative coordinator will develop a financial forecast. The forecast will be based on:

- Real and reimbursed cost per day
- EC contribution budget per partner (split in time and other cost)
- Distribution of budget in organisation (i.e. if more than one person will work on the project the Project Office needs to know the percentage of the budget to be spent on each individual)

This information is used to estimate the number of hours worked by each individual on the project. Distributed across the duration of the project, this provides a reasonable estimate of expected cost.

8.6 Exchange Rate

The exchange rate is one of the major risks particularly for the partners based in countries outside of Europe. In order to mitigate the risk, the initial financial forecasting should be done with a conservative estimate of the relevant exchange rate:

- For all costs incurred in non-Euro currencies (e.g. travel, accommodation) the official ECB exchange rate on the day that the cost was incurred must be used when claiming (this is the simple version that all organisations seem to follow).

8.7 Financial Claims

There are two main cost items related to the project: Staff cost and other cost (e.g., travel, subsistence). Both will be claimed on an ongoing basis using the project management system. For each of these there is a specific way of claiming them.

8.7.1 Confirmation of Claims

All partners will submit their costs to the administrative coordinator on a semi-annual basis. This will allow STRATEGIC to stay up to date with regards to the project budget. Partners are reminded that they need to keep records of all documents supporting claims in their usual accounting system.

8.8 Auditing

Only for requested EU contributions of EUR 430,000 or more, the respective beneficiary is obliged to submit a Certificate on the financial statements (CFS) at the end of the project. This does not affect any of the partners in the STRATEGIC consortium. However, the European Commission may request a project review at any time, up to 2 years after the final payment. According to article 25 of the Grant Agreement partners must keep their project records and documents for 5 years after the final payment.

9. Ethical Review of Research in the Project

All research involving human data collection or interaction with human subjects (including interviews, focus groups, workshops etc.) must be undertaken after proper ethics clearance. The responsibility for ethics approval rests with the WP leader of the WP in which the work is undertaken.

It should normally be sufficient to receive ethics clearance from the partner who leads the work and possibly the partner where the data is stored (if not identical). However, if data is collected in other jurisdictions from the one of the lead partners, then the partner undertaking the data collection needs to ensure that no further ethics approval is required in the jurisdiction where they collect the data. If further ethics approval is called for, then a relevant application can be based on the one originally received by the WP leader.

Data must only be collected once ethics approval is provided.

All ethics approvals need to be stored with the data, so that ethics audits can be quickly facilitated.

10. Data Management

The data management plan which forms part of the deliverable D7.3 (due in M6) will set out internal guidelines regarding data governance for the project.

11. Dissemination / Intellectual Property

Intellectual Property (IP) is governed by section 16 of the CA. The principle is that results are owned by the Party that generates them.

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16 with the following additions:

In case of joint ownership, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to Exploit the joint Results as it sees fit, and to grant non-exclusive licences, without obtaining any consent from, paying compensation to, or otherwise accounting to any other joint owner, unless otherwise agreed between the joint owners. The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related cost in advance.

It is not expected that the STRATEGIC project will lead to commercially viable IP. However, the work of the project will lead to exploitable result. Exploitation of project outcomes will form part of the standing agenda of all GA meetings.

11. Tools

There are a variety of project management and communication tools that can be used. Below is an indication of the original intention of usage which is subject to revision in the light of actual use.

11.1 Email

Email will be used as a notification tool and for communication on specific issues between partners. The STRATEGIC mail list will serve for most communication needs.

11.2 Teams

The UoN Teams / SharePoint site will be used to store all data and files that need to be shared and accessible.

All project members are therefore advised to ensure they have a Teams account and add it to the personal information in the directory.

11.3 Project Management Tool

The purpose is to provide a team and personal project management tool where you can assign tasks, schedule events, upload files, documents and more. It allows for all members of specific teams within STRATEGIC to have their own groups, their own to-do lists and much more.

12. Maintenance of the Handbook

This handbook will be continually updated by the STRATEGIC consortium in line with project requirements. The online version on the consortium repository will be the valid version.